

UZBEK ARTIST AND CREATIVE WORKS IN THE PERIOD OF INDEPENDENCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7327377>

Annotation: In this article noticed that in the purpose-of developing of aesthetic thoughts of young generation through fine arts and artistic creative work to analyse art works, to develop philosophical ideas.

Key words: reflex, perspective, aerial idea, flare.

МУСТАҚИЛЛИК ДАВРИДА ЎЗБЕК РАССОМИ ВА ИЖОДИЙ ИШЛАРИ

Аннотация: Мазкур мақола тасвирий санъат ва бадиий ижод орқали ёш авлодни эстетик тафаккурни ривожлантириш мақсадида, санъат асарларини таҳлил этиш, фалсафий ғояларни ривожлантириш масалаларини илгари суради.

Калит сўзлар: рефлекс, переспектива, фазовий тасаввур, блик.

УЗБЕКСКИЙ ХУДОЖНИК И ТВОРЧЕСКИЕ РАБОТЫ В ПЕРИОД НЕЗАВИСИМОСТИ

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы формирования философского и эстетического мышления молодого поколения посредством анализа произведений искусств.

Ключевые слова: рефлекс, переспектива, воздушная представления, блик.

INTRODUCTION

Through the discipline of graphic art the feeling of beauty enriches the spiritual outlook in increasing the creative ability in a person's mind in order to bring up a new generation in the spirit of perfectness. It is necessary to study the talented representatives of the art and their works from artistic point of view in esthetic upbringing of the young generation through graphic art[1].

At the beginning of the third Millennium the artistic culture of Uzbekistan intends to meet the contemporary needs. It is observed in all the branches of disciplines and culture, as well as in the branch of "The psychology of artistic feeling", which is relatively new for the republic.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

As it is known, creative works are arised according to the regularities of beauty. The graphic art is intervined with the disciplines of philosophy and psychology.

It is peculiar to mix the contrasted theories and ideas, to use the different methods for works in the jenre of picture in contemporary Uzbek graphc art. Modernism was a lonely method before the independence, rejecting in its structure abstarctionizm, suprematizm, surrealism and other branches.

The combination of the realistic schools with archaicks in the past is seen in modern art. This synthesis creates a new plastic language in graphic art. Majority of artists spontaneously learn the art of the range of countries of the world during the years of Independence. They have an opportunity to see their works, to analyze and to conduct new research against the background of the world graphic art.

The theory of art united with psychology in early XX. However, they have developed the society's outlook in different shapes, having a great impact on each other.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The interrelations between art and psychology became deeper and proved that the impact of the creative work traced back to psychologic mechanisms while explaining the influence of the art on the person.

In the threshold of Independence the new directions appeared in the graphic art of Uzbekistan.

The new traditions of Uzbek graphic art were observable. The examples for them are compositions as sketches and shapes as the main means of the compositions based on the myths and legends.

The international exhibition, organized by the Uzbekistan Art Academy, the Ministry of the culture and sports, the fund “” the forum of the culture and art of Uzbekistan”, Tashkent city Hokimiyat is one of the great events.

All the necessary conditions are created in the republic so that the people can take delight in watching the world and national masterpiece and the artists can create effectively and fruitfully. In the result of it the majority of artists, the talented young painters get success participating with their outstanding piece of art in the international exhibitions and national competitions.

The palaces of culture, galleries and exhibition halls founded by the initiative of the president of our republic, art educational establishments serve to bring up the perfect, cultured and harmonious youth and increase virtuosity of the young people[2].

It has also taken place in the goals and objectives of the modern international Tashkent art workshop, the international exhibition “Art is a symbol of humanity and creation”, which has been traditionally holding since 2001. The works of creators have never been so enormous in bringing people to benevolence, culture and cooperation as in this period of globalization.

The basic aim of the exhibition is to introduce the achievements in art and culture to foreign and native art amateurs and create the conditions to favourable creative communication of artists and art historians. Therefore, the interest and attention to the conference arise on the international level. Mainly, in the workshop of the modern art, which will be held on March, 6 in Tashkent the artists of many countries such as Great Britain, Belgium, Azerbaijan, the Ukrain, Russia, Iran, Singapour, China, South Korea will participate. The current workshop is being held under the motto “Modern art: society and the territory of the artist”. The presented works devoted to the views of the artistic esthetic performance of the society depicted in different genres and methods.

DISCUSSION

The regular art weeks, graphic art exhibitions, colourful cultural educational events, presentations, conferences arise the people interest to the art.

The bright example to it is the exhibition in the National Art centre, devoted to the works of Akmal Nur, the People artist of Uzbekistan.

The consecutive mechanism to recreate the national traditions and values, to make perfect culture and art, to support and encourage the creators was formed. The activities devoted to the given issues became primary in the fund “Forum of culture and art of Uzbekistan”.

The projects, various events, art exhibitions, creative festivals and concerts help to present our artists' works in our native land and abroad, thus making the great contribution to the national culture and art.

The works of Akmal Nur are famous among native and foreign art amateurs by its identity and singularity. The works draw attention of people not only by the national spirit, peculiar features of Uzbek folk but also by the combination of the modern traditions in art. The following works

“Carnation”, “Three brides”, “The gleamy mountain”, “Mood” considered to be the outstanding among his eighty works.

Furthermore, the “Art Week Style” presentation of the book, including the exposition of all his works became a grandiose event.

The main founder of the art week Style.uz Fund Forum pays attention to supporting the well-known representatives of the art, art historian and scientists by publishing monographs, researches, fundamental scientific investigation, catalogues and albums. One more interesting project is publishing the catalogue of the People artist of Uzbekistan, the academician of the Art Academy of Uzbekistan, the member of the Fund Forum.

Akmal Nur is one of the capable artists of the contemporary graphic art of Uzbekistan, his works are the harmonious depicting of the East and West traditions and the national peculiarity. The purpose of his works is to preserve the bases of the philosophical outlook and the classical oriental traditions and along with it they are distinguished by the unison of the modern person’s outlook.

CONCLUSION

By the initiative of Fund Forum 346 works were included in the album. The metaphor, enigmatic appearance and oriental symbol are combined in his works. The topic of love plays a major role in his works. It is not coincidence, because the topic has a significant importance in the East. He depicts the love not only to a definite person, but also to the whole humanity, revealing the cultural perfectness.

The collection shows the works of the artist according to the themes. The contents of the catalogue are the texts and the pictures, including five units. The collection is aimed to the representatives of the graphic art, the art amateurs and the public.

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